

Oxidative effects of ceftriaxone on broilers

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Abstract

Ceftriaxone is a recent broad-spectrum antibiotic indicated in several bacterial diseases in broilers. This study was done to evaluate the oxidative effects in poultry industry. It was carried out on 90 healthy chickens 6 weeks old, classified into 3 major groups 30 in each major group (control groups, ceftriaxone 50 mg/kg/day groups, ceftriaxone 200 mg/kg/day groups). Each major group then divided into 3 groups (10 chickens in each) for administration on Ceftriaxone for one day, three days and five days. We declared that Ceftriaxone effect was variant on tissues. On liver tissues, we found that ceftriaxone produced oxidative damage however its effect on brain was protective more over kidney didn't affected.

Keywords: broiler, ceftriaxone, oxidative stress, growth

Introduction:

Ceftriaxone is a third-generation cephalosporin with potent bactericidal activity against a wide range of gram positive and gram-negative bacteria. The antibacterial activity of ceftriaxone is due to inhibition of cell wall synthesis. (Dwivedi *et al.* 2012). Ceftriaxone is widely used, because of its prolonged terminal half-life that allows a single dose per day. Hepatotoxicity caused by ceftriaxone appears depending on dose and duration of therapy (Galvão *et al.* 2014). Ceftriaxone showed in several animal studies a protective effect on brain tissues and kidney tissues as well. (Cui *et al.* 2014). Our aim in the present study is evaluation of safety of ceftriaxone following multiple oral dose administration in chicken.

Material and methods:

This work is performed for measurement of oxidative parameters SOD activity, and GSH level in blood, liver, kidney and brain. Moreover, MDA level in serum, liver, kidney and brain.

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Experimental chicks:

A total number of 90 unsexed one day old Cobb broiler chicks were obtained from the Ismailia-Miser Poultry Company, Ismailia, Egypt. In this experiment, the rations were formulated as starter and grower finisher diets. Council [Bibliography 1994]. Broilers randomly grouped into 3 groups as following:- Control, ceftriaxone therapeutic dose (50 mg / kg / day) (Sar *et al.* 2013) and ceftriaxone high dose (200 mg / kg / day) (Cui *et al.* 2014). Broilers are slaughtered in different treatment durations (one day, 3 days and 5 days) 10 birds in each duration. Ceftriaxone Purchased from Sandoz Company, vial 1 gm for Dissolution.

Methods:

Collection and preparing of blood, serum and tissue samples:

Blood and serum samples: Blood samples were withdrawn from slaughtering and the blood samples was divided into two parts, serum for estimation of MDA and whole blood for estimation of SOD and GSH.

Tissues sample: The broilers were dissected to obtain liver, kidney and brain tissues for determining SOD, GSH and MDA.

Oxidative markers tests: Determination of SOD activity according (Nishikimi 1972) and GSH level according (Beutler 1963) in blood, liver, kidney and brain. Determination of MDA level in serum, liver, kidney and brain according (Ohkawa et al. 1979). All parameters determined

using ready-made kits of Bio Diagnostics reagents, Egypt. All parameters are measured spectrophotometrically.

Statistical analysis: Comparison were carried by means using analysis of variance “F test” (ANOVA) where the appropriate statistical analysis was calculated using least significant difference “LSD”. The level of statistical significance was taken as $P < 0.05$. (Millerand . and Miller 2005).

Results

Blood SOD activity and GSH level and serum MDA level in ceftriaxone treated groups

Table (1): Effect of ceftriaxone 50 mg per day and 200 mg per day administration for one, three and five days on oxidative markers in blood

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	blood SOD U/g Hb	blood GSH mg/ dl	Serum MDA nmol/ml
Control 1st day	0.933±0.18b	52.43±5.51ab	12.39±1.40ab
Cef therapeutic dose 1st day	0.918±0.18b	52.33±6.59ab	13.33±1.52ab
Cef high dose 1st day	1.269±0.20ab	53.03±6.18ab	13.99±1.07ab
Control 3 days	0.918±0.18b	52.93±5.80ab	11.7±1.57ab
Cef therapeutic dose 3 days	0.928±0.19b	53.13±6.96ab	13.59±1.58ab
Cef high dose 3 days	1.419±0.20ab	58.41±6.55ab	12.24±1.17ab
Control 5 days	0.905±0.17b	51.43±6.12ab	12.29±1.69ab
Cef therapeutic dose 5 days	1.76±0.17a	46.16±5.42b	15.15±1.35a
Cef high dose 5 days	1.79±0.19a	64.4±6.71a	11.14±1.19b

values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters are significantly different.

Liver SOD activity and GSH level and MDA level in ceftriaxone treated groups

Table (2): Effect of ceftriaxone 50 mg per day and 200 mg per day administration for one, three and five days on oxidative markers in liver.

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	liver SOD U/gm	liver GSH mg / g tissue	liver MDA nmol/g
Control 1st day	1.37±0.17a	2600±265.56a	109.55±9.70c
Cef therapeutic dose 1st day	1.355±0.12a	2604±248.75a	109.55±9.40c
Cef high dose 1st day	1.155±0.16abc	2534±214.36ab	110.05±9.05c
Control 3 days	1.409±0.17a	2570±263.48a	108.75±9.94c
Cef therapeutic dose 3 days	1.165±0.11ab	2554±227.01ab	114.38±9.84bc
Cef high dose 3 days	0.805±0.08bc	1800±169.97c	141.73±8.47a
Control 5 days	1.399±0.17a	2624±264.23a	108.65±9.64c
Cef therapeutic dose 5 days	1.125±0.13abc	1921±177.60bc	140.28±8.20ab
Cef high dose 5 days	0.775±0.07c	1580±192.53c	159.6±10.67a

values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters in the same column are significantly different.

Kidney SOD activity and GSH level and MDA level in ceftriaxone treated groups

Table (3): Effect of ceftriaxone 50 mg per day and 200 mg per day administration for one, three and five days on oxidative markers in kidney.

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	kidney SOD U/gm	Kidney GSH mg / g tissue	Kidney MDA nmol/g
Control 1st day	0.4742±0.08a	340.3±30.42a	52.25±4.67a
Cef therapeutic dose 1st day	0.483±0.07a	333.9±28.09a	53.65±5.45a
Cef high dose 1st day	0.4543±0.08a	339.1±29.83a	52.15±4.68a
Control 3 days	0.4843±0.07a	336.3±28.59a	52.75±4.98a
Cef therapeutic dose 3 days	0.4733±0.08a	337±29.19a	54.1±5.36a
Cef high dose 3 days	0.4422±0.07a	338.1±29.82a	51.95±4.70a
Control 5 days	0.4893±0.07a	339.5±30.02a	53.05±4.71a
Cef therapeutic dose 5 days	0.4602±0.07a	339.6±30.07a	53.95±5.25a
Cef high dose 5 days	0.4542±0.07a	336.4±30.19a	50.75±4.98a

values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters in the same column are significantly different

Brain SOD activity and GSH level and MDA level in ceftriaxone treated groups

Table (4): Effect of ceftriaxone 50 mg per day and 200 mg per day administration for one, three and five days on Oxidative markers in brain

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	Brain SOD U/gm	Brain GSH mg / g tissue	Brain MDA nmol/g
Control 1st day	0.2515±0.02c	316.3±19.87b	226.8±15.62a
Cef therapeutic dose 1st day	0.2541±0.02c	318.2±19.54b	228.2±15.22a
Cef high dose 1st day	0.2583±0.02c	333.6±24.26ab	234.8±14.39a
Control 3 days	0.2522±0.02c	316.7±20.34b	229.6±15.18a
Cef therapeutic dose 3 days	0.2563±0.02c	323±19.63b	230.8±14.77a
Cef high dose 3 days	0.324±0.02ab	379.7±31.39ab	212.3±12.86ab
Control 5 days	0.2485±0.02c	317.4±20.13b	227.4±15.39a
Cef therapeutic dose 5 days	0.2791±0.03bc	329.6±20.63ab	234.8±14.39a
Cef high dose 5 days	0.358±0.02a	392.7±31.83a	174.9±15.37b

values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters are significantly different.

Discussion:

Ceftriaxone is widely used as a third-generation cephalosporin antibiotic that has a broad spectrum of bactericidal activity. ROS are generated from endogenous metabolic processes (redox reactions) or due to exposure to drugs or chemicals and xenobiotics (Al-Sayed *et al.* 2014). Deleterious effects caused by ROS occur as a result of an imbalance between the formation and inactivation of these agents leading to disturbance in normal cellular

physiology and different pathological conditions Ibrahim . and Abdel-Daim [Bibliography 2015]. Free radicals have been implicated in the pathogenesis of many degenerative diseases (Rehman . and Akash 2017). Regarding the effect of ceftriaxone on oxidative status in blood the study results in table (1), groups treated with ceftriaxone 200 mg for 5 days and groups treated with ceftriaxone 50 mg for 5 days showed significant increase in SOD activity, these results come in accordance

with **Dwivedi [Bibliography 2014]** who used Ceftriaxone in a dose of 155 mg/kg/day for 5 days which had led to increased level of SOD activity in blood, moreover GSH level and also decreased level of MDA because ceftriaxone enhanced the free radicle scavenging properties, more over **Lapenna et al. [Bibliography 1995]** stated that antioxidant effect of ceftriaxone may cause depression of its antibacterial activity and suggested that the drug antioxidant group may protect the beta lactam ring against radicles attack. It was suggested by **Lapenna et al. [Bibliography 1995]** that Ceftriaxone enhances free radicles scavenging and chelating ability properties, it was reported that it is effective drug for removal of arsenic intoxication in rats which improves the endogenous antioxidant defense system. In the glue of previous notion **Alexander et al. [Bibliography 2012]** carried out a study on Ceftriaxone and declared that it increases SOD activity in plasma and brain. Moreover, increases activity of glutathione reductase in plasma. Which agreed with our results that ceftriaxone increases GSH level in plasma. Our results we observed that MDA level was increased in serum which agreed with **Yilmaz et al. [Bibliography 2011]** who reported that Ceftriaxone decrease the level of MDA in plasma and brain tissues by reducing the activity of myloperoxidase and xanthine oxidase (free radicles generating enzymes) Moreover Ceftriaxone increased the level of GSH in plasma. In addition, **Dwivedi et al. [Bibliography 2012]** stated that third generation cephalosporins and ceftriaxone showed chelating property that compete with microorganisms for any of the trace iron and calcium ions which are essential to the maintenance to the their life cycle, they penetrate the cell membrane and open the calcium channel and enhanced bacterial cell death, and also added that Cephalosporin's antibiotics showed free radicle scavenger property and their effect on inhibition of neutrophil function. On the other hand **Galvão et al. [Bibliography 2014]** studied

Ceftriaxone 50 mg /kg/ day on lung tissues and they declared that ceftriaxone induced oxidative damage in lung tissues, they found that treatment with ceftriaxone causes imbalance of antioxidant enzymes, and administration of antioxidants with ceftriaxone were restoring the SOD/CAT ratio in rats with severe respiratory infection. As it were well known that SOD activity produces hydrogen peroxide, which in the presence of transition metals, can induce cell membrane damage by lipid peroxidation or react with iron to generate hydroxyl radicals via Fenton chemistry. CAT can remove the excess of hydrogen peroxide, limiting the oxidative damage. The increased SOD and CAT activity in septic rats are in keeping with the observations that enzymatic antioxidant defenses are able to induce lung injury. Also **Ware [Bibliography 2006]** noted that Ceftriaxone 50 mg / day cause reduction of the total thiol content in the lung of pabeo animals treated with ceftriaxone and The amount of MDA increased (1.5 times) in the lungs of ceftriaxone group. **Cojocel et al. [Bibliography 1985]** provide one possible explanation for this is that ceftriaxone is able to generate hydroxyl radical which can further contribute to the additional formation of other reactive species such as singlet oxygen. So, ceftriaxone showed controversy results depending on its location, dose and duration of treatment. As shown in table (2) SOD activity and GSH level in liver were significantly decreased in both groups treated with ceftriaxone 200 mg/kg/ day for 3 and 5 days and in groups treated with ceftriaxone 50 mg/kg/ day. As shown in table (2) MDA level in liver in groups treated with ceftriaxone high dose for 3- and 5-days duration of treatment and group treated with ceftriaxone therapeutic dose for 5 days duration of treatment showed significant increase in comparison with control group. Meanwhile groups treated with ceftriaxone therapeutic dose for 1- and 3-days duration of treatment and group treated with ceftriaxone high dose for 1-day

duration of treatment showed non-significant change in comparison with control group. The previously mentioned results come in accordance with **Dwivedi et al. [Bibliography 2012]** who found that Ceftriaxone induces oxidative damage by generation of hydroxyl radicle which is well-known as it is one of the most reactive oxidizing radicle with limited diffusion, in other words hydroxyl radicle will not diffuse a significant distance within the cell before reacting with biomolecules and cause damage within small radius of its site of production. Also **Cohen . and Nyska [Bibliography 2002]** stated that The reactivity of hydroxyl radicals is extremely high In contrast to superoxide radicals that are considered relatively stable and have constant, relatively low reaction rates with biological components, hydroxyl radicals are short-lived species possessing high affinity towards other molecules, OH. is a powerful oxidizing agent that can react at a high rate with most organic and inorganic molecules in the cell, including DNA, proteins, lipids, amino acids, sugars, and metals. The 3 main chemical reactions of hydroxyl radicals include hydrogen abstraction, addition, and electron transfer. OH. is considered the most reactive radical in biological systems; due to its high reactivity, it interacts at the site of its production with the molecules closely surrounding it. This reactivity indicates that the radicle will be injurious to cells only if the metal catalyst is localized on biomolecules essential for survival. Reaction of hydroxyl radical includes its ability to interact with the purine and pyrimidine bases of DNA abstraction of hydrogen atoms from many biological molecules, as stated by **(Asmus 1990)**. Glutathione is one the affected biomolecules from hydroxyl radical. The previous data confirmed our results which revealed the significant decrease in GSH level in liver. Moreover increased MDA level in liver which comes in accordance with **Chakraborty et al. [Bibliography 2005]** Who ensured that ceftriaxone

induced lipid peroxidation when incubated with liver homogenate which corroborates earlier observation of MDA. This study results declared that Ceftriaxone had a dose dependent manner in its oxidative damage effect on liver tissues and these findings come in accordance with **Alhumaidha et al. [Bibliography 2014]** who found that a markedly significant decrease in the level of hepatic GSH. Conversely, the level of hepatic MDA (a marker of lipid peroxidation) obviously increased. The increase in MDA level was more pronounced in rats treated with ceftriaxone 360 mg/kg/day than ceftriaxone 180 mg/kg/day. and these obtained results were due to ROS generated from ceftriaxone which can oxidize sulfhydryl groups present in the amino acid cysteine **(Kim et al. 2000)**. As Ceftriaxone doesn't cause any deleterious effect on kidney tissues, as shown in table (3) these results come in accordance with **Abdel-Daim [Bibliography 2016]** who declared that ceftriaxone has powerful antioxidant properties seem to mediate such protective effect, directly by scavenging ROS and inhibition of lipid peroxidation. As shown in table (4) SOD activity in brain showed significant increase in only groups treated with ceftriaxone high dose for 3- and 5-days duration of treatment, while, GSH level in brain showed significant increase in only group treated with Ceftriaxone high dose for 5 days duration of treatment. Unlike MDA level in brain showed significant decrease in only group treated with Ceftriaxone high dose for 5 days duration of treatment. These previously mentioned results agreed with **Hussein et al. [Bibliography 2016]** who demonstrated that ceftriaxone 200 mg /kg /day easily crosses the blood–brain barrier moreover Ceftriaxone increased SOD activity and lower MDA level in brain, moreover Ceftriaxone demonstrated a neuroprotective effect in form of attenuation of oxidative damage and down regulation of Cx-43 expression which clarified the antioxidant effect of

ceftriaxone. Also, **Puttachary et al. [Bibliography 2015]** explained the effect of ceftriaxone as neuroprotective and antioxidant probably by up regulation of glutamate transporter 1 resulting in reduction of glutamate chemical transmitter and Ca²⁺ overload which are the main role involved in enhanced production of ROS. It was postulated that oxidative stress and ROS play an important role in development of epilepsy because oxidative stress resulting from mitochondrial dysfunction gradually disrupts the intracellular calcium hemostasis which modulates neuronal excitability and synaptic transmission making neurons more vulnerable to additional stress. Meanwhile, **Lin et al. [Bibliography 2013]** added that Glutamate transporter 1 is the most abundant glutamate transporter in brain and plays a principle role in keeping of glutamate concentration low by removing the glutamate released at the synapse, Ceftriaxone has a neuroprotective potential via prevention of down regulation of glutamate transporter 1. Furthermore, **Lai et al. [Bibliography 2008]** reported that administration of ceftriaxone could suppress neuronal autophagy in hippocampus of rat brain. **Wei et al. [Bibliography 2012]** declared that ceftriaxone could reduce the multiplex inflammatory cytokine levels (interleukin-1 β , interferon- γ , and tumor necrosis factor- α). In addition, ceftriaxone is the most widely used antibiotic has no substantial toxic central nervous system actions at therapeutic dose 50 mg/kg/day. Therefore, normal ceftriaxone doses are likely to be sufficient to up-regulate glutamate transporter 1. Concerning GSH level in brain in table (4) which showed significant increase in only group treated with Ceftriaxone high dose for 5 days duration of treatment, these results agreed and explained by **Whanger [Bibliography 2001]** who recognized that ceftriaxone down regulate Glutamate, which is the principal excitatory neurotransmitter in brain and neurons. Excess glutamate at the

synapse leads to inhibition of cysteine uptake which is precursor for glutathione synthesis. GSH-Px uses glutathione as substrate. A decrease reduced GSH-Px activity was observed on expose to oxidative stress which could be due to the presence of excess glutamate at the synapse that competitively inhibits cysteine uptake which in turn in the precursor for glutathione synthesis. All of the animal disease model in which ceftriaxone was found to be protective show signs of oxidative stress as mentioned by **(Soni et al. 2009)**

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